

Coumaryl 6-*iso*Thiocyanate.

BY BIMAN BIHARI DEY AND TIRUVENKATA RAJENDRA SESHADRI.

6:6'-Dicoumarylthiocarbamide is formed on boiling an alcoholic solution of 6-aminocoumarin with carbon disulphide. The reaction is ordinarily very slow, but is accelerated as usual by the addition of small amounts of sulphur. The use of sodium hydroxide which is generally employed for such condensations is inadvisable in this case, as it causes decomposition of the thiocarbamide. The latter is remarkably stable, however, in presence of acids, and may be boiled with concentrated hydrochloric acid without undergoing any change.

Thiophosgene has been found to be a suitable reagent to employ for the preparation of the *isothiocyanate* from the aminocoumarin. Dyson and George (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 125, 1702) state that the reaction between aniline and thiophosgene proceeds in the following manner,

the intermediate phenylthiocarbamyl chloride, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{Cl}$, being actually isolated by them. The interaction of aminocoumarin and thiophosgene in dry benzene solution gave a product which could not be obtained pure but which probably corresponded to the thiocarbamyl chloride as it readily decomposed in contact with water into aminocoumarin hydrochloride and coumarylthiocarbimide. A better and purer yield of the thiocarbimide was obtained by carrying out the reaction in aqueous medium (*cf.* Dyson and George, *loc. cit.*), the amount of thiocarbonyl chloride used being slightly in excess of that required according to the following equation:—

The objectionable nature of thiophosgene made it desirable to search for a process in which the use of this reagent could be dispensed with altogether, and it was found that the method worked out

by Werner (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1891, **59**, 396) could be applied with success to the present case. When dicoumarylthiocarbamide is boiled with acetic anhydride, a vigorous reaction ensues and the carbamide is converted almost quantitatively into a mixture of acetylamino-coumarin and coumaryl isothiocyanate, thus:

The thiocarbimide is readily separated from the acetylamino-coumarin which is much more soluble in acetic acid. The reactions of this thiocarbimide with a few amino- and hydroxy compounds are also described.

EXPERIMENTAL.

6: 6'-Dicoumarylthiocarbamide.—6-Aminocoumarin (2 g.) was boiled for 6 hours with alcohol (30 c.c.), carbon disulphide (10 c.c.) and sulphur (0.5 g.). The clear solution slowly deposited a bulky amorphous solid which was filtered and washed, first with carbon disulphide and then with dilute hydrochloric acid. It was very sparingly soluble in the common organic solvents but could be crystallised from boiling nitrobenzene as colourless rhombic prisms, m.p. 250-52° (yield 2 g.). (Found: N, 7.8; S, 8.5. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{S}$ requires N, 7.7; S, 8.8 per cent.).

The substance readily dissolved in alkali hydroxides to form yellow solutions from which it could be reprecipitated by acidifying; it remained unchanged on boiling with concentrated hydrochloric acid or on treating with concentrated sulphuric acid at 100° or even on boiling with acetyl chloride for half an hour. It was decomposed on continued boiling with caustic potash.

Coumaryl-6-thiocarbimide: (1) *From dicoumarylthiocarbamide.*—Dicoumarylthiocarbamide (2 g.) was boiled with acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) over a sand-bath for about 5 minutes. The resulting clear solution, on cooling, was filled with a thick mass of colourless needles. Water was then added and the mixture boiled to decompose all acetic anhydride, and filtered hot. The residue, which was almost pure, was further boiled twice with small quantities of dilute acetic acid and filtered.

The product crystallised from benzene as colourless needles, m.p. 186-87° (yield 70 p. c.). (Found: N, 7.1; S, 15.9. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{NS}$ requires N, 6.9; S, 15.7 per cent.),

The combined acetic acid filtrate deposited, on cooling, a bulky crystalline precipitate and a further quantity was produced on neutralising the solution with ammonia. It crystallised from boiling water as colourless flat needles melting at 220-21° and was found to be identical with 6-acetylamincoumarin.

(2) *From 6-Aminocoumarin and Thiocarbonyl Chloride.*—Thiocarbonyl chloride in aqueous suspension was treated with a little less than three molecular quantities of 6-aminocoumarin which was added in small quantities at a time, the reaction mixture being warmed up to 60° and stirred mechanically. The bulky amorphous precipitate was filtered, washed with dilute hydrochloric acid, dried on a porous plate and twice crystallised from boiling benzene, using animal charcoal, when 6-coumarylthiocarbimide was obtained as colourless needles, m.p. 186-87°. It was identical with the product obtained from the dicoumarylthiocarbamide mentioned above.

It is insoluble in water, dilute mineral acids or dilute alkali solutions and it is only slowly decomposed by glacial acetic acid to produce acetylamincoumarin. When a boiling alcoholic solution of the substance is mixed with a similar solution of 6-aminocoumarin a bulky precipitate of 6:6'-dicoumarylthiocarbamide is obtained.

Monocoumaryl-6-thiocarbamide was slowly deposited as heavy colourless crystals when a boiling alcoholic solution of the thiocarbimide was treated with an excess of concentrated aqueous ammonia. It could be easily crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 234-35° (decomp.). (Found: N, 12.9. $C_{10}H_8O_2NS$ requires N, 12.7 per cent.).

Phenyl-6-coumarylthiocarbamide was obtained in two ways, *viz.*, by boiling for about two hours a solution in alcohol or benzene of equimolecular quantities of (1) 6-coumarylthiocarbimide and aniline and (2) phenylthiocarbimide and 6-aminocoumarin. The product was filtered, washed thoroughly with dilute hydrochloric acid and after drying on a porous plate, crystallised from benzene. It came down as colourless rectangular prisms, m.p. 169-70° (decomp.). (Found: N, 9.6. $C_{16}H_{12}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 9.5 per cent.).

When the product obtained by its decomposition at the melting point was repeatedly crystallised from nitrobenzene, it melted at 252°, and was found to be identical with 6:6'-dicoumarylthiocarbamide.

Phenyl-6-coumarylthiosemicarbazide was produced in a crystalline condition by boiling equimolecular quantities of coumarylthiocarbimide and phenylhydrazine in benzene solution for an hour. After

cooling and filtering, it was washed with small quantities of hot benzene and later, with dilute hydrochloric acid. It then crystallised from boiling benzene as colourless needles, m.p. 171-72°. (Found: N, 13.4. $C_{16}H_{13}O_2N_3S$ requires N, 13.5 per cent.).

Ethyl coumaryl-6-thiocarbamate was obtained as thin plates when an alcoholic solution of coumaryl-6-thiocarbimide was boiled under reflux for 5 hours and then cooled. After recrystallisation from alcohol it melted at 167-68°. (Found: N, 5.4. $C_{12}H_{11}O_3NS$ requires N, 5.6 per cent.).

6-Thio-p-tolylaminocoumarin was prepared by adding anhydrous aluminium chloride to a solution of coumaryl-6-thiocarbimide in dry toluene and heating it on the water-bath for 2 hours. On pouring the product into water a flocculent precipitate was obtained which crystallised from alcohol as pale yellow needles, m.p. 253-54°. (Found: N, 4.9. $C_{17}H_{13}O_2NS$ requires N, 4.7 per cent.).

6:6'-Di-4:7-dimethylcoumarylthiocarbamide was obtained in good yield from 6-amino-4:7-dimethylcoumarin and carbon disulphide. It crystallised from nitrobenzene as colourless prisms, m.p. 258-60° (Found: N, 6.8. $C_{23}H_{20}O_4N_2S$ requires N, 6.7 per cent.).

4:7-Dimethylcoumaryl-6-thiocarbimide was prepared by the same two methods as have been described in the case of coumaryl-6-thiocarbimide. It crystallised from boiling benzene as colourless needles, m.p. 235°. (Found: N, 6.2. $C_{12}H_9O_2NS$ requires N, 6.1 per cent.).

In boiling alcoholic solution it combines with 6-amino-4:7-dimethylcoumarin to produce 6:6'-di-4:7-dimethylcoumarylthiocarbamide; with concentrated ammonia it yielded *mono-4:7-dimethylcoumarylthiocarbamide* as large prisms, m.p. 241° (decomp.), and with aniline it formed *4:7-dimethylcoumarylphenylthiocarbamide* crystallising in rectangular prisms, m.p. 192° (decomp.).